

Employee Recruitment, Selection and Retention in Saudi Arabian Family Owned Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs)

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Abstract

FOSMEs (Family Owned Small and Medium Scale Enterprises) represent more than 90 percent of enterprises in Saudi Arabia, providing 51 percent of jobs in private sector and contributing 22 percent of GDP. Employee recruitment, selection and retention is always related with performance outcomes of the organization, including SMEs. 70 percent of SME managers say they lack skilled workforce and managing employee retention is a big challenge. The aim of the present research is to investigate the current practices in employee recruitment, selection and retention in family owned SMEs, so that new models can be developed. The researcher adopted the quantitative and qualitative approaches; the data was collected by using questionnaires and semi-structured interviews using convenience sampling. The totals of 150 questionnaires were distributed to the targeted SME managers / owners, using purposive convenience sampling. Out of the 150 administered questionnaires, 120 were returned, out of which 100 were selected upon which the analysis is based. The results suggests that majority of FOSMEs do not have a formal HR department; do not have HR Policies and practices. word of mouth, news paper advertisements, referrals, agencies e-recruitment are some of the popular recruitment techniques and English language, math's test , interviews, medical test are some of the popular selection techniques and factors like good relations, recognition, salary, medical benefits are important for employees to work longer. The results from this study will facilitate the owners, entrepreneurs and managers of FOSMEs to face the challenges of lack of qualified labor and high employee turnover rates and also meeting the Saudization targets.
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Keywords: Family Owned Small and Medium Scale Enterprises, Recruitment, Selection, Retention, Employee Turnover

1. Introduction and problem statement

At the international level, SMEs are providing 80 percent of jobs in the private sector and contributing 47 percent of world GDP. In Saudi Arabia SMEs are providing 51 percent of jobs in private sector and contributing 22 percentage of GDP (Abdul Ghafour, 2013). According to the Saudi Arabian Monetary Agency (SAMA) statistics. The family owned small and medium enterprises constitute 90 % of total companies in Saudi Arabia and representing 51% of total employment in the country, and contributes a revenue of 232.5 Billion Saudi Rials (\$ 62 Billion), SMEs contributes 28% of industrial production in Saudi Arabia and employed around 300,000 employees and providing many job opportunities to Saudi nationals helping the government in Saudization (a local nationalization program in Saudi Arabia).

A comparison of recruitment and selection practices at large and small enterprises were investigated by Barber, Wesson, Robersin, and Taylor (1999) found that two recruitment areas are not same, and should be managed differently. On the contrary to this, Hornsby and Kuratko (1990) suggest that SMEs perform more improved HR practices similar to larger organizations. Ongori (2010) found that the effective employee recruitment, selection and retention are key factors to the entry point of human resources in any organization, which also tends to determine the success and sustainability of SMEs. Windolf (1986) found that the firms less than 20 employees implement easy attitude towards employee recruitment, selection, which intern could lead to high employee turnover. This same statement was made by Cook (1998) with the new point on infrequent and inconsistent recruitment, selection experiences can lead to higher employee turnover. SMEs, often do not devote time and discipline to an effective recruitment and selection process, this in turn can lead to lower retention rates (Barrier 1999). Under the back-drop these reports and surveys, the importance of employee recruitment, selection and retention in success of SMEs

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cannot be undermined in the growth of SMEs in Saudi Arabia. It becomes obligatory to study the current practices in family owned SMEs in Saudi Arabia and so that improvements can be made through offering new solutions to help the owners/ managers to manage challenges related to employee recruitment, selection and retention. Currently there is no evidence of such literature or a research before.

1.1. Research Objectives

- To investigate the existing methods of recruitment, selection and retention used in family owned small and medium scale businesses in Saudi Arabia
- To investigate the issues faced by family-owned SME's in employee recruitment, selection and retention
- To recommend a model / checklist to assist family owned SME's owners to be more effective in recruitment, selection and retention of employees

1.2. Research Questions:

The study proposes to investigate and seek answer to the following research questions (RQ)

- RQ1- Do the family owned SME's in Saudi Arabia have formal HR Department with policies and practices?
- RQ2- How does the family owned SME's in Saudi Arabia recruit their employee? And what recruitment methods do they use?
- RQ3- How does the family owned SME's in Saudi Arabia select their employee? And what employee selection methods do they use?
- RQ4- How do the family owned SME's in Saudi Arabia retain their employees?
- RQ6- What are the issues faced by family owned SME's in Saudi Arabia in relation to employee recruitment, selection and retention

1.3. Significance of the study

The study seeks to contribute to the non-existing knowledge and explore the possibilities to provide solutions to improve the existing practices related to employee recruitment, selection and retention in Saudi Arabian family-owned SMEs as there was no research study was organized on this area. The results from my study will facilitate the entrepreneurs / owners / managers of family owned SME's to deal with the challenges of recruitment, selection and retention and effectively manage their human resources to attain their objectives and to be efficient, well trained to manage these functions.

2. Litature Review

2.1. Definition of recruitment and the empirical evidence on essence of recruitment in family-owned SMEs

Recruitment is a process of seeking applicants to fill recently vacated or newly created positions using a variety of methods (Snell and Bohlander 2010, p.188), . Recruitment is a process of 'seeking and attracting a pool of

applicants from which qualified candidates for job vacancies within an organization can be selected.' (Stone, 2005, p. 12). According to Hornsby and Kuratko (1990), SMEs are frequently unable to afford Human Resource Management staff and, therefore, their owner/managers have to perform such duties as recruitment and selection themselves. Deshpande and Golhar (1994) suggested that small and large firms used almost identical methods of recruitment. This result is somewhat different to others discussed later in this review. Deshpande and Golhar (1994) found, however, that job posting, followed by promotion, referrals, temporary staff, transfers, advertisements, employment agencies, educational institutions, and finally previous applicants was the order in which they were ranked.

For many family-owned small businesses, Aitkinson and Meager (1994) suggest that external recruitment is a most critical aspect for the small business, as it occurs infrequently, and External recruitment provides new blood and fresh ideas, while reducing inbreeding and resentment of internal favourites. However, external recruitment can also be very expensive in competitive times of high employment (Compton et. al., 2002, p.52). For family-owned small business, the costs can lead to their inability to vie for skilled staff. McEvoy's (1984) research found that 67 per cent of recruitment in small business was achieved by means of walk-ins or advertising. Carroll et. al. (1999) confirmed that word-of-mouth contacts had distinct advantages for family-owned small business. Speed and cost were two of the main advantages. Recruitment is not without its difficulties. For example, Mehta (1996) found that 25 per cent of small businesses surveyed reported that a lack of qualified workers was a threat to their plans. Hornsby and Kuratko (1990) found that obtaining sufficient numbers of quality workers from which to recruit was a most important issue. Williams and Dreher (1992) found that the higher the pay levels in a business, the larger the pool of people willing to work for that business. Williamson, Cable and Aldrich (2002) found 25 per cent of the small businesses that they studied said that slow economic growth was the most important issue they faced, while 50 per cent nominated scarcity of qualified employees as their most important problem. Accordingly, the following research questions are posited

2.2. Definition of selection and the empirical evidence on essence of selection in family-owned SMEs

Employee selection is a process of choosing individuals who have relevant qualifications to fill existing or projected job openings (Snell and Bohlander, 2010, p.254). In family-owned small business, one of the most important requirements in the matching process of selection is for the employee to 'fit in' (Holliday, 1995; Carroll et. al., 1999). Tests are frequently found to be too expensive for family-owned small firms to use because they need to be conducted by professionally trained staff. For the family-owned small business it would appear that the most appropriate tests to utilize would be the personality tests as both (Holliday, 1995; Carroll et. al., 1999) found in their studies that the most important factor in introducing a new employee into a family-owned small business is not their aptitude for the position, but their ability to fit in. The selection interview is used as one of the key recruitment activities in small business and is anticipated by both the applicant and employer alike. The interview has three main objectives. Firstly, it is used to assess the suitability of the applicant. Secondly, it is used to ensure that sufficient information is made available for the candidate to make a decision, and finally, it is used as a public relations exercise (Plumbley and Williams, 1981). McEvoy's (1984) research confirmed that 90 per cent of selection techniques used in small business were done by interview or application blanks.

2.3. Definition of employee retention and the empirical evidence on essence of employee retention in family-owned SMEs

Employee retention refers to the various policies and practices which let the employees stick to an organization for a longer period of time. Irrespective of the size, if the companies are unable to retain their talented employees, it will be very difficult for their survival. (Management, 2012). Luna-Arocas and Camps (2008) re-examined the impacts of salary, job enrichment and job stability, previously examined by Bloom and Milkovich (1999, p. 40). They found that salary was an 'important staff retention strategy ... [and a] precursor of turnover intention in both direct and indirect ways'. Herriot (1989) asserts that key employees have career expectations that need to be met. If their aspirations are not met, they will search elsewhere for work that can satisfy their potential. Employers frequently

presume pay and perks are rewarded with good performance on the job (Herriot, 1989, p. 77). However, employees may require much more benefits like flexible working hours, paid holidays, bonus, health insurance, pension and more. Hutt (2005, p. 43) identified that in order to contribute to relationship longevity, ‘leaders need character development with an emphasis on values, and ethics’.

2.4. Definition of SMEs in Saudi Arabia and its role in economic development

When we discuss, SMEs its very important to define it as SMEs definition differs in each country depending on the factors of number of employees, annual sales turnover. In Saudi Arabia, SGIA (Saudi Arabian General Investment Authority) classified companies based on the number of labor is as follows:

Type of enterprise	Number of employees
Small Size Enterprises	Less than 59
Medium Size Enterprises	60-99
Large Scale Companies	More than 100

SMEs in Saudi Arabia represent 90 percent of total enterprises, the industry-wise, 47% of SMEs are engaged in commercial and hotel businesses, 27% in construction field, 12% industrial manufacturing sector, 6% in social services and 8% in other different businesses (SAGIA, 2007). In Saudi Arabia SMEs are providing 51 percent of jobs in private sector and contributing 22 percentage of GDP (Abdul Ghafour, 2013).

3. Methodology

Research Methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem, it describes various steps adopted by the researcher in studying his research problem along with the logic behind them (Kothari C.R, 2012, p.8). The present study proposes to adopt qualitative and quantitative approaches to address the research questions, qualitative method is used to make an enquiry into current practices of employee recruitment, selection and retention in family owned SMEs in Saudi Arabia by using surveys collect data. Quantitative approach will be used to specifically answer the research questions, with suitable justifications and causal explanations. This mixed methodology is identified most appropriate in view of the exploratory nature of the study. In this research, structured questionnaires are used to examine the existing conditions relating to recruitment, selection and retention of staff instrument, The data was collected by using questionnaires and semi-structured interviews using convenience sampling. The totals of 150 questionnaires were distributed to the targeted SME managers / owners, using purposive convenience sampling. Out of the 150 administered questionnaires, 120 were returned, out of which 100 were selected upon which the analysis is based.. Targeted respondents were te owners / managers / supervisors of family owned SMEs from Jeddah, Riyadh and Dammam cities.

4. Data Analysis, results and inferences

4.1. Demographic profile of owners / managers: Table 1 indicates descriptive demographic characteristics of respondents who are either the owners or the managers of family-owned SMEs. A total of 100 responses were received.

Table 1. Demographic profile of FOSMEs

S.No	Variable(s)	Percentage
1.	Gender	
	Male	42
	Female	58

2.	Age	
	Less than 20 years	3
	21-30	28
	31-40	20
	41-50	14
	51-60	35
	60 and above	
3.	Marital Status	
	Single	20
	Married	65
	Unstated	15
4.	Educational Levels	
	No education	30
	Primary school	19
	High school	4
	Secondary school	10
	First Degree	17
	Masters	8
	Professional Diploma / certificate	12
5.	Experience	
	0-2	10
	3-5	12
	6-10	15
	11-15	23
	16 and Above	40

Source: Developed for this research

4.2. Demographic profile of businesses: Table 2 indicates descriptive demographic characteristics of FOSME businesses

Table 2. Demographic profile of FOSMEs

	Variable(s)	Percentage
1.	Origin of Business	
	Established the business	21
	Inherited from parents	68
	Purchased as established business	8
	No response	3
2.	Type of Industry	
	Fashion Design	
	Retail	23
	Beauty saloon	12
	Healthcare	3
	Construction	25
	Hotels, Restaurants and Tourism	22
	Manufacturing	15
3.	Employees who are family members	
	Family Member	65
	Non-Family Member	35
4.	Size of the organization	
	10 and Less	20
	11- 20	22
	21-40	32
	41-59	2
	60-99 (Medium Size Enterprises)	12
	100 and Above (Large Scale Companies)	12

Source: Developed for this research

4.3. *Descriptive Statistics:* The manager / owner(s) of FOSMEs who responded in the study provided data on their current recruitment, selection and retention methods, pertaining descriptive statistics can be found below

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of primary data

S.No	Variable(s)		FR	P	CP	Inference
1	The extent to which FOSMEs have HR Policies and Procedures	NA	60	60	60	28 percent of family-owned SMEs use formal HR policies and procedures and 72 percent indicated that they rarely or do not use formal HR policies and procedures. These findings confirm with established literature. Kotey (1999) found that SME owners / Managers do not have formal HR practices, Carroll et al (1999), Mathis and Jackson (1991) and Deshpander and Golher (1994) also confirmed that SMEs have little adoption of recommended systematic HR procedures.
		R	12	12	72	
		S	10	10	82	
		F	5	5	87	
		GE	13	13	100	
2	The extent to which FOSMEs employ HR Specialists	NA	48	48	48	Only 26 percent of family-owned SMEs use HR specialists, while 74 percent indicate that they rarely or never employ HR specialists in their organizations to manage HR functions.
		R	26	26	74	
		S	11	11	85	
		F	5	5	90	
		GE	10	10	100	
3	The extent to which FOSMEs use Saudi Labour Law in decisions related to their employees	NA	8	8	8	88 percent of family-owned SMEs indicate that they follow Saudi labour law, while only 12 percent indicate they rarely or never follow the Saudi labour law in decisions related to employees.
		R	4	4	12	
		S	2	2	14	
		F	23	23	37	
		GE	63	63	100	

Source: Developed for this research, Legend: FR= Frequency, P=Percentage, CP=Cumulative Percentage; NA= Not at all, R= Rarely, S=Sometimes, F=Frequently ; GE=Great extent

4.4. *Recruitment methods used by family-owned SMEs:* The respondents were also asked to specify the employee recruitment methods they adopt out of selected recruitment methods to nominate from. These recruitment methods are shown below:

Table 4. The use of various recruitment methods in employment of staff

Type of recruitment method used	Mean score on 1-7 Likert scale	Inference
Word of mouth	4.3	Indicates most popular methods of employee recruitment in family-owned SMEs is word of mouth with mean of 4.3 on seven point Likert Scale. Newspaper advertisements, ranked second with a score of 3.8, followed by employee referrals, walk-ins, promotions. Point to be noted is none of these FOSMEs are using social media, retired employees and campus recruitment as a source of recruitment. These findings are in confirmation with the
Newspaper Advertisements	3.8	
Employee referrals	3.2	
Walk-Ins	2.4	
Promotions	2.2	
Sign-in shop front	1.9	
Recruitment Agencies	1.8	
Company Websites / Job sites	1.0	

Social Media	0.0	established literature, Carrpll et al. (1999) , Holliday (1995) also found that word of mouth is the most preferred in SMEs for searching staff. Deshpander and Golhar (1994) found that job postings are the most popular method followed by promotion, employee referrals, advertisements, job agents and educational institutions.
Retired Employees	0.0	
Campus recruitment	0.0	

Source: Developed for this research

4.5. *Selection methods used by family-owned SMEs:* The below table enlists the employee selection methods used by family-owned SMEs, ranked in order of mean scores based on the responses from the managers / owners of SMEs:

Table 5. The use of various recruitment methods in employment of staff

Type of selection method used	Mean score on 1-7 Likert scale	Inference
CV filtering based on specific criteria	5.8	Shows the employee selection methods ranked in order of its popularity , CV filtering based on the criteria as rated highest followed by interview, group interview, medical examination, educational achievement verification, aptitude test etc. None of the enterprises is using psychometric testing as part of the employee selection process. These findings are in line with the available literature. De Milia and Smith (1997) and Townley (1994) found that application forms are most popular screening tool in SMEs and McEvoy (1984) , Carroll et al (1999) found that in 90 percent SMEs use interviews, tests in employee selection.
Interviews	5.7	
Group Interviews	5.1	
Medical Examination	4.6	
Educational Achievement verification	3.2	
Aptitude Tests (Language / Quantitative)	3.1	
Preliminary Telephonic interviews	2.3	
Background / reference checking	2.1	
Application forms	1.9	
Online Interviews	1.5	
Psychometric Tests	0.0	

Source: Developed for this research

4.6. *Employee retention methods used by family-owned SMEs:* The table below lists the employee retention strategies by family-owned SMEs ranked in order of mean scores based on the responses.

Table 6. Extent of the use of various methods of employee retention

Type of retention method used	Mean score on 1-7 Likert scale	Inference
Good relationship with supervisors	6.1	Shows the methods used to retain employees ranked based on mean scores, Good relationships with supervisor was rated highest with a mean score of 6.1 on seven-point Likert Scale, while the good relationship with colleagues ranked second, followed by employee involvement, overtime, flexible working hours, family status, bonus / incentives etc. These findings are not confirmed by Herriot (1989) who found that pay packages, perks, employee autonomy are important in retaining the staff. Hutt (2005) work focussed on employee coaching as an important element for retention. Martel (2003) identified that freedom to take risks, tolerating mistakes, listening to employees, being transparent, offering share ownership, training and development are important factors in employee retention
Good relationship with colleagues	5.9	
Employee involvement	5.2	
Overtime	5.1	
Flexible working hours	5.0	
Family Status	5.0	
Bonus / incentives	4.8	
Pay package	4.8	
Accommodation	4.6	
Medical benefits	4.2	
Transport facilities	3.2	
Child care benefits	2.9	
Annual leave	2.8	

Source: Developed for this research

4.7. *Issues affecting the employee recruitment, selection and retention in family-owned SMEs :* The below lists the factors affecting the organizational ability to recruit, select and retain staff effectively, ranked based on the mean scores identified by the respondents.

Table 7. Issues that affect the employee recruitment, selection and retention at family owned SMEs

Type of issue	Mean score on 1-7 Likert scale	Inference
Skills shortage	4.6	

Government regulations & employment law	4.6	The results identify that skills shortage to fill a vacancy position, government regulations are the most important issue affecting employee recruitment, selection and retention with a mean score of 4.6, the other issues include saudiazation, company ability to offer competitive compensation etc. These issues are confirmed with the available literature. Jones (2003) found that labor shortage, labor law, cash bonuses are important factors affecting SME recruitment and retention. Williamson et al.(2002) found that slow economic growth, and scarcity of qualified employees are important problems faced by SMEs
Demand for Saudiazation	4.3	
Ability to offer competitive compensation	3.9	
Type of business	3.4	
Economic conditions	3.1	
Political conditions	3.0	
Business location	2.1	
Working conditions	2.0	

Source: Developed for this research

5. Conclusion and recommendations:

The study provides insights into the current practices in employee recruitment; selection and retention in family-owned SMEs in Saudi Arabia revealed that the employers are adopting more laissez-faire methods of checklists, rather than traditional HRM methods followed by big businesses, these practices might place their businesses at disadvantage in terms of their ability to recruit, select and retain the best talents in the competitive market. It is recommended that these companies follow modern HR tools like HR Planning, Job Descriptions, Job Specifications, Social Media recruitment, usage of psychometric testing and online interview methods and most importantly organizing campus placements can benefit them to find young talent with modern ideas. Orientations, Training programs, employee involvement, fair pay, fair rewards / incentives, flexibility in working hours, health & safety programs, developing grievance handling mechanisms, maintaining positive relationship between employees, coaching, mentoring and providing trust based inspirational leadership can enhance the chances of employee retention. The family-owned SMEs should also employ HR Specialist to deal with recruitment, selection and retention issues, develop HR Policies, ensure that the performance appraisals are implemented fairly and linked to employee development programs. SMEs should embrace a positive HR philosophy and strive to follow modern HR models.

6. The way forward for further research

The findings of this study would add to the literature on family-owned SMEs recruitment, selection and retention practices which appears to be nonexistent specifically in Saudi Arabia and also serve the basis for future research. The study is however limited to the fact that data for this investigation was collected from three cities Jeddah, Riyadh and Damam, which may not be a representative of entire country. There is also a need to apply statistical techniques like exploratory factor analysis (EFA) in form of principal component analysis to reduce the large number of variables into small set of factors, using ANOVA to compare significant differences and regression analysis. The future research must focus on other cities and rural areas in Saudi Arabia with a large sample size to give a realistic picture of recruitment, selection and retention practices in family-owned SMEs in Saudi Arabia.

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